

THE MAIN APPROACHES TO THE SEMANTIC CLASSIFICATION OF BEHAVIORAL VERBS IN THE SCIENTIFIC LITERATURE

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From birth to old age, a person communicates with his type, performs certain actions. The set of principles of behavior in which a single person reacts to the life of society is called social behavior. The peculiarities of behavior, human relations with other people are reflected in the oral dictionary, which is a socially significant branch of the national picture of the world. Philosophers view behavior as a person's ability to work in the material, intellectual and social spheres of life, and this is conditioned by natural and environmental factors. Psychologists and teachers often understand behavior as synonymous with activities that have natural conditions, but are based on the mediation of socially conditioned, language and other sign-semantic systems, the typical forms of which are cognition, work, play, communication; this is a certain way of organized activity that connects the organism with the environment.² lawyers interpret this as "socially significant behavior of citizens and officials, provided for by the norms of the law and with certain legal consequences." "Sociologists associate human behavior with social programs and values established in the material and spiritual culture of society. At the same time, it is regulated by both individual and social consciousness, as well as social institutions and legal norms, ethics and politics. In ethics, behavior is a set of human actions of moral importance, since they can be assessed morally (both intentionally and intentionally).

The lexical-semantic groups of behavioral verbs of the Russian language were the first to R. M. Gaisina, who identified and described their lexical-syntactic compatibility models. They have been studied in terms of semantics, component composition, word formation [3 et al.], functional potential [2], in terms of cognitive approach. Today, interest in the semantics of Word formation of verbs of Russian behavior has revived, in particular, stereotypes and models of behavior presented in the lexical and word formation semantics of Russian verbs are described. A. M. Aidarova's work is devoted to the comparative study of behavioral verbs based on Russian, English and Tatar. English verbs denoting informal behavior are recorded among mask verbs (masquerade Verbs): Action, treatment, camouflage, counting, masquerade, officiate, pose, read, title, rate, service B. In a well-known classification by Levin [9, 183-184]. R. In Dickson's

classification, some verbs of English behavior are considered in terms of syntactic semantics. Mention of English verbs that express behavior R. It also occurs in Liber's work, where the group of verbs-ize, -ify with the meaning of similarity stands out (the meaning of analogy).

Person lives and acts by performing certain actions as a product of nature and society. The peculiarities of human behavior are widely reflected in the oral dictionary, where his relations with other people are a very wide group. Within the framework of the study, the lexical-semantic group of verbs of behavior in different structured languages seems necessary to consider the basic concept of "human behavior", based on methodological approaches developed in different social and humanitarian disciplines, since this concept has an interdisciplinary status.

Behavior is the subject of the study of many areas of human science (psychology, philosophy, sociology, ethics, etc.). L.M. Popov proposes to distinguish the following three groups of subjects in the study of human behavior : 1) thinking, non-evaluative (philosophy, psychology, Ethology, sociology); 2) thinking, evaluative (ethics); 3) evaluative-transformational (pedagogy, law) [l. M. Popov 2008].

Scientific ideas about human behavior developed rapidly at the beginning of the 20th century, when representatives of behaviorism (from the English "behavior"- "behavior") declared it a subject of psychology. Behavior was then understood to be any measurable reactions (e.g. speech, motor, etc.) is an organism that works according to a " stimulus – reaction " scheme. At the same time, it was noted that people interact with the world around them and change it and themselves undergo changes as a result of their actions [Skinner 1957: 1]. Later, the content of this concept was replenished and deepened.

Several approaches and concepts are included in the theoretical foundations of the study of verbs that express behavior in languages. One such approach is semantic analysis of verbs, which makes it possible to identify different aspects of the behavior described in the language. This approach involves the study of semantic fields and semantic relations between verbs.

Another approach is the functional analysis of verbs, which allows us to determine the role of verbs in communication and social interaction. This approach involves exploring different contexts of verb use, such as formal and informal situations, their relationships with other parts of speech, etc.

The third approach is cognitive analysis of verbs, which allows us to determine the connection between language and thinking. This approach

involves the study of cognitive processes related to the use of verbs such as describing, classifying and classifying objects and phenomena.

In addition, various theoretical concepts such as acting theory, frame theory, scenario theory, etc. are used in the study of verbs that express behavior. These concepts allow the analysis of the relationship between verbs and the social context in which they are used.

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